

21st Century Skills of Students through Pedagogical Practices of the Teacher: An Assessment

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ABSTRACT

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This research assessed the pedagogical practices of a mathematics teacher and the 21st century skills of ABM (Accountancy, Business, and Management), GAS (General Academic Strand), and STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand) students at Casiguran Technical Vocational School, Sorsogon, Philippines. This case study employed the mixed of qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection, including classroom observation, documentary analysis, and student surveys. The findings showed that the teacher utilized varied pedagogical practices to develop the critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, self-direction, making local connections, and using technology for learning. However, there were areas for improvement in creativity, self-direction, and local connections. The assessment of student 21st century skills indicated proficiency in critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity, self-direction, making local connections, and using technology. The study concluded that innovative pedagogies positively influenced skill development and developed a 21st century skills teacher's guide. Recommendations included prioritizing the development of 21st century skills using innovative pedagogical practices and promoting problem-solving abilities. The develop teacher's guide may be subject for validation of school authorities and will then be adopted by other schools, and further research in other grade levels and subjects is suggested.

KEYWORDS:

Instructional Strategies, Critical Thinking Skills, Communication Skills, Self-Direction Skills

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main problems in schools today is to help students learn 21st century skills. This is important because the world is changing fast due to globalization. These skills include what students know, how they work, and the kind of person they become. They help students do well in school, in jobs, and in life (Moyer, 2016; Rotherham & Willingham, 2009). Students need these skills to solve hard problems, work with others, learn on their own, and keep up with the fast changes in the world (Gewertz, 2008). Schools all over the world should teach these skills not just to students, but also to the community and everyone involved. The most important 21st century skills are critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, self-direction, making local connections, and using technology as a tool for learning. Teachers need to help students learn these skills.

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Also, schools need to do more than just teach for tests and grades. Schools should help students become smart thinkers, strong learners, and creative problem solvers who help their communities. The Department of Education (DepEd) says it is important to teach 21st century skills to students. They want students to go beyond simple lessons and find real ways to help their lives and fight corruption in the government (L. Briones, personal communication, February 23, 2019). Right now, schools in the country are still undergoing transitional phase to teach 21st century skills. There are programs like workshops and seminars for teachers and students. Other opportunities to improve include the National Seminar-Workshop on Rethinking Education, scholarships for teachers to study more, and the 21st Century Learning Environment Model (CLEM) Classroom. These help teachers and students build their skills. To make sure students are ready for the world, teachers must teach, show, and check these 21st century skills (Department of Science and Technology, 2018). Teachers are very important in building a better country. So, it is important to look at what teachers

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are doing in class and how it helps students learn these skills (Ragas, Pontillas, & Comon, 2024).

This study aims to help schools improve how teachers teach and how students learn 21st century skills. By checking what teachers do now and how students learn, we can find better ways to teach these skills.

II. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table I: Students' Observed Learning Outcomes along 21st Century Skills with Teacher's Pedagogical Practices

21 st Century Skills	Teacher's Pedagogy & Instructional Strategies	Observed Students Learning Outcomes	Students' Level of 21 st Century Skills	
			Pre-Survey	Post-Survey
Critical Thinking Skills	<p>Socratic Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of HOTS Questions Throwing Motive Questions Use of Real-Life Experiences <p>Problem Based Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to Real-World Problems Small Group Collaboration Asking Probing Questions <p>Inquiry Based Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questioning Techniques Small Group Collaborations 	<p>Defines the topic under investigation by examining it through various perspectives.</p> <p>Gathers information from multiple relevant, timely, and credible sources, using a variety of collection methods.</p> <p>Considers multiple accounts or explanations before formulating conclusions; shifts own thinking in response to new information or different perspectives.</p>	C (2.58)	C (2.64)
Collaboration Skills	<p>Collaborative Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Think-Pair-Share Small Group Collaboration Feedback & Support Reflection & Self-Assessments <p>Project Based Learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small Group Collaboration Solving Real-World Problems <p>Conducive Environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring a positive environment Encouraging Reflection and Self-Assessment 	<p>Fulfills various roles and responsibilities in order to complete the task and meet the goals.</p> <p>Shares leadership in defining roles, assigning tasks, and fulfilling responsibilities.</p> <p>Adheres to agreed-upon group norms to ensure collaboration and sharing of ideas.</p> <p>Facilitates compromise among group members to achieve goals.</p> <p>Shares concerns, insights, and resources with the group.</p> <p>Submits products that meet the detailed specifications for the assigned task.</p> <p>Accurately reflects on the quality of the work; uses reflection and feedback to revise ideas.</p>	C (2.72)	C (2.71)
Communication Skills	<p>Socratic Method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questioning Techniques Peer Engagement Cooperative Learning Student Presentations Peer Feedback 	<p>Enhances contribution by contributing ideas, asking or responding to questions, and building upon or challenging other's comments.</p>	C (2.61)	C (2.66)

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	<p>Problem Based Learning Team Presentations Peer Feedback</p> <p>Reflective Writing</p> <p>Guided Questions</p>	<p>Applies a variety of verbal and nonverbal active listening strategies to support communication.</p> <p>Uses appropriate digital tool to clearly communicate a message in audio and visual.</p> <p>Responds communications in a timely manner.</p> <p>Seeks out, selects, and uses resources and strategies to achieve goals for improving communication skills.</p>		
Creativity & Innovation Skills	<p>Problem Based Learning Real-World Problems Open-Ended Problems Divergent Thinking</p> <p>Cooperative Learning Brainstorming Peer Feedback</p> <p>Differentiated - Instruction</p> <p>Evaluation</p>	<p>Defines the problem or challenge by examining it through various lenses</p> <p>Generates multiple, plausible ideas using a variety of strategies.</p> <p>Seeks and considers unfamiliar ideas with an open mind.</p> <p>Makes connections between and builds upon others' ideas to generate new and unique insights.</p> <p>Effectively integrates resources to develop a solution.</p> <p>Completes a product according to plan and meets all specifications, making changes as necessary.</p>	C (2.58)	C (2.64)
Self-direction Skills	<p>Self-directed Learning Real-World Problems</p> <p>Problem Based Learning Small Group Collaboration</p> <p>Metacognitive Strategies Self-Monitoring</p> <p>Self-Reflection</p>	<p>Applies strategies to set achievable goals, seeking minimal assistance.</p> <p>Occasionally needs redirection to focus on the learning process.</p> <p>Applies strategies and problem solves with occasional teacher assistance.</p> <p>Monitors learning progress and self-corrects with occasional teacher guidance.</p> <p>Selects and uses appropriate resources with minimal teacher guidance.</p> <p>Occasionally reflects upon learning independently, identifying the strengths and weaknesses, using feedback, and modifying work.</p>	C (3.01)	C (2.93)

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Local Connections	Contextual Learning Guided-Reflection Authentic Assessments	Investigate topics or issues that are relevant to the family or community with occasional teacher guidance. Occasionally apply the learnings to local situations, issues or problems.	C (2.82)	C (3.03)
Using Technology as a Tool for Learning	Inquiry Based Learning Use of technology for research purposes Blended Learning Use of digital components to provide a mix of teacher-led & self-directed learning experiences Collaborative Learning Use of technology tools for communication & file sharing	Uses technology to products work products with little assistance. Uses appropriate technology tools to collect information with little assistance. Uses appropriate technology to communicate ideas with little assistance. Seeks appropriate technology resources to solve problems. Uses technology properly. Complies with rules regarding the ethical use of technology.	C (2.73)	C (2.81)

The survey results reveal mixed outcomes across the seven assessed skills. While some skills, such as making local connection and using technology as a tool for learning, showed notable improvement, others, such as self-direction skills and collaboration skills, exhibited a decline.

The significant improvement in local connection (+0.21) suggests that the activities effectively contextualized learning within the students' communities. Strategies emphasizing relatable, real-world applications likely contributed to this outcome. The slight increase in using technology as a tool for learning (+0.08) indicates moderate success in integrating digital tools into learning activities. However, the limited gain may reflect challenges such as unequal access to technology and insufficient opportunities for hands-on practice.

Both critical thinking skills (+0.06) and creativity and innovation skills (+0.06) showed only marginal improvement, highlighting potential limitations in the pedagogical strategies employed. For instance, structured activities like Problem-Based Learning (PBL) may have focused on achieving predefined outcomes, restricting opportunities for divergent thinking and exploration. Although there was a slight improvement in communication skills (+0.05), the gain was minimal, suggesting that while group discussions and presentations were incorporated, more targeted activities to enhance verbal and written communication are needed.

Among seven skills, collaboration skills (-0.01) and self-direction skills (-0.08) declined. The slight decline could indicate that students struggled with group dynamics or faced challenges in effectively working together. Limited time or unclear roles during group activities may have contributed to this outcome. Meanwhile, the decline in self-direction skills is concerning and may reflect a lack of activities promoting autonomy and independent learning. Students may have relied heavily on teacher guidance during tasks, limiting opportunities to set goals, self-monitor progress, or reflect on their learning.

The teacher's pedagogical strategies for developing critical thinking skills included the Socratic method, Problem-Based Learning (PBL), and Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL). These approaches encouraged students to think critically and apply mathematical concepts to real-world scenarios. By presenting authentic, open-ended problems related to their topics, the teacher guided students to collaboratively analyze the problem, identify relevant concepts, and develop solutions. Although Problem-Based Learning (PBL) encourages students to tackle real-world problems, its structured nature may limit opportunities for open-ended exploration and divergent thinking, a key aspect of creativity. Similarly, while self-direction involves independent goal-setting and problem-solving, students accustomed to teacher-led instruction may struggle to adapt without additional scaffolding or support.

From the start of the semester, students were grouped to foster collaborative learning. Group work allowed them to

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brainstorm and learn together, enabling peer evaluation, which helped students assess their learning progress and growth. During a lesson on graphing functions, for instance, students brainstormed in groups, assigning specific tasks to each member. One served as the secretary, documenting solutions and answers, while another acted as the presenter, sharing the group's output with the class. These practices facilitated the development of collaboration skills as students worked cooperatively to solve problems and communicate their findings.

To promote communication skills, the teacher established a rotation scheme, ensuring that each group member had the opportunity to present and discuss their solutions with the class. During group activities, one representative from each group presented the solutions and answered questions from peers and the teacher. Prior to these presentations, groups would brainstorm, allowing each member to contribute insights. According to one student respondent, these presentations enhanced their communication skills by allowing them to articulate ideas and respond to questions in front of an audience.

In a lesson on functions as a model, creativity and self-direction were further nurtured through activities like short story writing and poster-making. Students were asked to write a reflective story about an experience, either in school or at home, and then visually represent that experience. Reflective questions such as "What did you learn from this experience?" and "How does this story relate to the concept of a function?" encouraged students to think critically about the connections between personal experiences and mathematical concepts. Through these tasks, students developed communication skills (through writing), creativity (in their artwork), and self-direction (by reflecting on their learning and experiences). Students took responsibility for their own learning by reviewing their work and responding to feedback from peers and teachers. To reinforce their learning, some students conducted independent research online, consulted additional textbooks, sought help from older students, or held group study sessions during free time. Self-direction was evident as students regularly reviewed their work before presenting it to the class, aiming to ensure quality and incorporate feedback for improvement. Furthermore, classroom observations revealed that students engaged more actively in collaborative tasks than in individual reflective activities. While group activities on real-world applications of mathematical functions promoted teamwork and communication, tasks requiring independent initiative such as reflective journaling were often completed minimally. This indicates a need for more targeted interventions to support self-direction, such as metacognitive strategies or guided reflection.

One activity exemplifying the real-world application of math concepts involved identifying situations that illustrate functions. Students provided examples such as daily allowances, electric bills, water bills, and food budgets. Through this exercise, they recognized the relevance of mathematical functions in everyday life and how these skills could help solve practical problems, thereby developing their ability to make local connections.

Although students had a one-to-one ratio of general mathematics textbooks, they also consulted additional resources as recommended by their teacher. They accessed online resources like Khan Academy, Purple Math, WikiHow, and YouTube. Students without smartphones accessed these resources through computer shops or relied on peers to share information. Additionally, they used scientific calculator apps on their smartphones to check graphs in lessons on rational functions, which helped them verify the accuracy of their work.

Lastly, students used group chats on Messenger for easy communication and collaborative support. These group chats allowed them to share academic files, ask questions, track assignment progress, and strengthen teamwork, contributing significantly to their collaborative skills.

Figure 1 below demonstrates students' critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and innovation, self-direction, and skills in making local connections through their completion of the assigned task. The task, which focused on operations on functions, provided an engaging, meaningful, and hands-on experience. The limitations involving volume and surface area challenged students to think critically about the mathematical relationships involved in the dimensions of a cube. They needed to analyze the problem, utilize their prior knowledge of functions, and employ strategies to meet the requirements. To complete the task, students collaborated with their groupmates by effectively communicating and listening to different perspectives to construct a cube.

This process not only strengthened their ability to articulate ideas and explain reasoning but also honed their teamwork and problem-solving abilities. Moreover, by using recycled materials and experimenting with designs, students tapped into their creativity, demonstrating resourcefulness and innovation. As they managed their time, took ownership of the activity, and responded to reflective questions, they improved their self-direction skills. By utilizing community-sourced materials and being mindful of environmental impacts, students developed an appreciation for making local connections, fostering awareness of their surroundings and promoting sustainable practices. This activity, being group-based, emphasizes the importance of collaboration in achieving the intended outcomes. However, a possible discrepancy lies in the varying levels of participation among

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group members, which may affect the unbiased development of skills. Some students might rely on others to complete tasks, potentially hindering their growth in self-direction and critical thinking. Additionally, while the use of recycled materials is commendable, limited resources in some settings may restrict creativity and innovation, highlighting the need for balanced access to resources.

Figure 1: Teacher’s Activity on the topic Operations on Functions

Enrichment/ Application: Group Task
Topic: Operations on Functions

Objective/s:
1. Perform multiplication of functions
2. Construct a box satisfying a given volume

Direction: Using a recyclable material (like used cardboard, extra wood, scrapped metals, etc.) construct a box containing a volume of 1,000 cubic centimeters and a surface area of 600 square centimeters.

Reflective questions:
1. What is the connection of the box in the concept of operation of functions?
2. How was your preparation in making your output?
3. What challenges have you encountered in accomplishing the task?
4. Cite at least 5 possible uses of the box you have made.

Volume = $x^3 = (10\text{cm})^3 = 1000\text{cm}^3$
Total Surface Area = $6x^2 = 6(10)^2 = 600\text{cm}^2$

the table, notable increase was found in GAS along critical thinking skills, local connections, and using technology as a tool for learning. GAS students showed the most notable improvement in critical thinking skills (+0.17, 2.61 to 2.78), moving further into the "Proficient" category. This increase may be due to the strand's broad curriculum, which exposes students to diverse problem-solving activities and interdisciplinary subjects. The flexibility of the GAS curriculum likely enables students to engage in varied scenarios that challenge their analytical thinking. However, to sustain this growth, more structured critical thinking exercises, such as case studies or scenario-based discussions, could further enhance these skills. Further, GAS students made the most progress in local connections (+0.18, 3.15 to 3.33), reaching the "Advanced" level. This may stem from the strand's generalist approach, allowing students to explore local issues or contexts more thoroughly. Group tasks and contextualized-based projects likely supported this growth by enabling students to relate their learning to real-world problems. This improvement highlights the value of practical, locally relevant applications in developing 21st-century skills. GAS students also demonstrated significant improvement in using technology as a tool for learning (+0.36, 2.71 to 3.07), achieving a solid "Proficient" rating. The focus on technology integration in the curriculum could have encouraged students to enhance their digital skills. This suggests that the availability of technological tools and opportunities for digital collaboration were effectively leveraged in the GAS strand. Continued use of technology-focused projects, such as multimedia presentations or online research tasks, could further support this growth.

The table 2 below shows the presurvey and postsurvey result of ABM, GAS, and STEM strands along different skills. In

Table II: Students’ Observed Learning Outcomes along 21st Century Skills with Teacher’s Pedagogical Practices

21 st Century Skills	ABM		GAS		STEM		F-TEST	
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Critical Thinking Skills	2.5 (Proficient)	2.64 (Proficient)	2.61 (Proficient)	2.78 (Proficient)	2.62 (Proficient)	2.49 (Basic)	0.3290 (NS)	2.3303 (NS)
Collaboration Skills	2.6 (Proficient)	2.67 (Proficient)	2.84 (Proficient)	2.82 (Proficient)	2.76 (Proficient)	2.64 (Proficient)	0.5901 (NS)	0.4462 (NS)
Communication Skills	2.64 (Proficient)	2.63 (Proficient)	2.7 (Proficient)	2.74 (Proficient)	2.52 (Proficient)	2.6 (Proficient)	0.6499 (NS)	0.2070 (NS)
Creativity & Innovation Skills	2.6 (Proficient)	2.61 (Proficient)	2.82 (Proficient)	2.76 (Proficient)	2.46 (Basic)	2.56 (Proficient)	2.1845 (NS)	0.6192 (NS)
Self-direction Skills	2.9 (Proficient)	2.9 (Proficient)	3.15 (Proficient)	2.97 (Proficient)	3 (Proficient)	2.92 (Proficient)	0.6351 (NS)	0.0429 (NS)
Local Connections	2.49 (Basic)	2.69 (Proficient)	3.15 (Proficient)	3.33 (Advanced)	2.82 (Proficient)	3.06 (Proficient)	3.1312 (NS)	5.6703 (S)
Using Technology as a Tool for Learning	2.67 (Proficient)	2.62 (Proficient)	2.71 (Proficient)	3.07 (Proficient)	2.8 (Proficient)	2.73 (Proficient)	0.1640 (NS)	3.9634 (S)

Legend: (S) Significant, (NS) Not Significant

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There were also notable decreases in the survey outcomes along different skills. STEM students experienced a decline in critical thinking skills (-0.13, 2.62 to 2.49), moving from "Proficient" to "Basic." This decrease could be linked to the technical nature of the STEM curriculum, which may prioritize precision and content mastery over open-ended problem-solving. Time constraints or a lack of emphasis on reflective practices may have limited the development of critical thinking. To address this, more problem-based learning activities and opportunities for open discussion on complex scenarios could help bridge this gap. STEM students also saw a drop in collaboration skills (-0.12, 2.76 to 2.64), though they remain "Proficient." This decrease might stem from the individualistic focus of STEM tasks, such as lab work or mathematical problem-solving, which often prioritize individual accuracy over teamwork. Introducing interdisciplinary group projects or peer-assisted learning activities could help students build better collaboration skills within the STEM strand. Hence, GAS students experienced a slight decline in self-direction skills (-0.18, 3.15 to 2.97), although they stayed "Proficient." This decrease may reflect limited opportunities for independent tasks or insufficient emphasis on fostering autonomy. Introducing more project-based learning or self-paced assignments could encourage GAS students to take greater ownership of their learning and recover this skill.

On the other hand, through analysis of variance, results revealed that there's a significant change along local connections and using technology as a tool for learning. Using the Tukey test, it revealed that there's a significant difference in the means of ABM and GAS during the posttest. Results show that GAS students achieved the highest gains in local connections, improving from 3.15 to 3.33, classified as "Advanced." This indicates that the GAS strand's activities effectively emphasized real-world and contextualized-based applications, likely fostering a strong understanding of how their skills connect to their environment. Meanwhile, ABM students improved from 2.49 to 2.69, moving from "Basic" to "Proficient." This suggests progress but highlights a gap between ABM and GAS in this area. The significant difference in posttest means between ABM and GAS may stem from the generalist and interdisciplinary nature of GAS, which naturally promotes broader contextual learning compared to the business-specific focus of ABM. Moreover, in using technology as a tool for learning, GAS students again demonstrated notable improvement, increasing from 2.71 to 3.07, both classified as "Proficient." This reflects a strong integration of digital tools in GAS activities, allowing students to explore and apply technology more effectively across various contexts. ABM students, on the other hand, showed a slight decrease from 2.67 to 2.62, remaining at the "Proficient" level. The minimal change in ABM could indicate a stable but less dynamic use of technology

compared to GAS. The significant difference between the two strands during the posttest highlights the need for ABM to incorporate more advanced and versatile technology-based tasks to catch up with the progress observed in GAS.

These findings suggest that pedagogical methods must balance structured and exploratory learning activities. Incorporating more opportunities for open-ended projects and self-assessment may help address the observed gaps in creativity and self-direction. Moreover, teacher training programs should emphasize strategies for fostering these competencies, such as promoting student autonomy and encouraging risk-taking in problem-solving.

Hence, the results of this study should be understood in the context of the challenges in education in the Philippines and worldwide trends in developing 21st-century skills. While the study shows that certain teaching methods are effective in promoting certain skills, it also points out deeply rooted problems that are similar to those faced in other educational systems around the world. For instance, the educational system in the Philippines faces ongoing challenges like a rigid curriculum, limited resources, and unequal teacher training. These challenges affect the development of 21st-century skills. For example, the emphasis on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) focuses more on delivering standard content and leaves little room for hands-on, skill-building activities.

Sumagaysay (2018) discusses how curriculum makers may fail to address the real needs of learners and highlights that rigid curricula can be influenced by insufficient resources. Additionally, there are differences in resources between schools, which make it harder for some students to develop key skills. Rural schools, often do not have the technology and materials needed to support creativity and independent learning. These findings match Mendoza's (2022) study, which showed that students in under-resourced schools in the Philippines struggle to participate in open-ended, technology-based learning activities. Moreover, the study's findings also connect with trends seen in other countries, especially in developing regions where resource shortages and traditional teaching methods slow down the development of 21st-century skills. For example, research in rural schools in India found that while collaborative learning improved teamwork, students had trouble adjusting to independent learning because they were used to teacher-centered methods (Patel & Sharma, 2021). Similarly, in sub-Saharan Africa, limited access to digital tools was shown to limit students' ability to develop technology skills (Adebayo, 2020). These shared issues show how educators in resource-limited areas face similar challenges. This study also adds something new by focusing on the differences in skill development across the ABM, GAS, and STEM strands that is often overlooked in global research. For example, the significant difference in critical thinking skills between STEM and ABM students highlights how different curricula can affect learning

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outcomes. This provides more understanding of how teaching methods can be designed to meet the specific needs of students in each track.

III. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the results, several key conclusions can be drawn. Firstly, the teacher respondent demonstrated a strong commitment to utilizing innovative pedagogical approaches in their lessons, with the aim of developing the 21st-century skills of their students. This suggests that the teacher recognized the importance of equipping students with the critical competencies needed for success in the modern world and proactively adopted engaging and effective teaching methods to foster the acquisition of these skills. However, the mixed outcomes among seven skills of the survey highlights several potential influencing factors including teacher experience, resource availability, and student demographics. Teacher experience likely played an important role in shaping these outcomes. The observed gains in critical thinking and communication skills align with the teacher's familiarity with structured methods, such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and the Socratic Method. However, fostering creativity and self-direction may require additional expertise in less traditional, exploratory strategies, which the teacher acknowledged during interviews as areas for personal development.

The findings also indicate that the students who were exposed to the teacher's diverse and innovative teaching practices exhibited greater confidence and competence in performing tasks and activities designed to cultivate their 21st-century skills. This positive outcome highlights the impact that the teacher's innovative pedagogical approach had on the students' ability to apply and demonstrate the targeted skills, such as problem-solving, critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and creativity. On the other hand, resource availability plays a crucial role in the development of 21st century skills in students especially in the Philippine education. For instance, access to online learning platforms, educational apps or programs, and self-paced learning materials supports students in taking charge of their learning. Teachers can guide students to use these resources for independent research or study, decision making, and problem solving, building their self-direction skills. Additionally, student demographics can also be a factor on the development of certain skills such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status. Age because older students may be more developed and ready to take on more complex activities and projects. Their maturity and cognitive development impact how quickly they can master skills like self-direction. Gender can influence how students interact with certain activities. Boys and girls may approach problem-solving differently, potentially affecting skills development. Therefore, teachers should create a more inclusive environments that support all

students equally in developing their skills. And students from low-income backgrounds may have limited access to technology, books, or extracurricular activities that are essential for skill development. This can hinder their ability to develop skills such as creativity, collaboration, and using technology as a tool for learning. In contrast, students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds might have more access to resources, leading to better skill development outcomes. Building on these findings, a 21st century skills development teacher's guide was developed. For students to be ready for the global world, K–12 teachers need to help them develop 21st-century skills. DepEd encourages teachers to create lessons that focus on these skills, but there are no clear or direct resources to help teachers achieve this. Teachers, as curriculum implementers, mostly follow the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) when making lesson plans. However, how they teach and what methods they use depend on them. DepEd's goal is good, but there is no system to ensure it will be achieved. For example, there are trainings about teaching in the 21st century, but they are not detailed enough to help teachers apply them properly. This practical guide aims to fill that gap. It will help teachers choose the right teaching methods to develop specific 21st-century skills. Unlike other guides that focus on a single competency, this guide will give teachers ideas about what methods work best for each skill. This is not a ready-made lesson plan, but it will be very helpful for teachers in making their own. Teachers still have the responsibility to create lessons that fit their students' needs, as they are the ones who know their learners best. This recommendation suggests that there is a recognition of the ongoing need to provide additional support, guidance, and opportunities for students to enhance their proficiency in the essential competencies required for success in the modern landscape. The developed teacher's guide could serve to reinforce and expand upon the foundational work done by the teacher in the classroom, ensuring that students are comprehensively equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary for their future endeavors.

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V. DISCLOSURE

Both authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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